

Trade Potential of India UAE Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA)

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines the impact of the India-UAE Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (IUCEPA) on the composition and the extent of bilateral trade between India and UAE. To understand the complementarity of trade structure and potential for trade cooperation, the paper employed indicators such as Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA), Revealed Trade Advantage (RTA) and Revealed Competitiveness (RC), along with trade specialisation analysis. To understand the trade impact of the IUCEPA agreement on both nations, an augmented gravity model with the Fixed Effect Vector Decomposition (FEVD) and Poisson Pseudo-Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimation techniques were used. The findings revealed that India has had a more stable comparative advantage compared to the UAE over the years. There exists complementary trade between the two countries. The overall impact of the CEPA is positive, with the trade projected to increase to US\$113 billion within five years of signing the agreement. The study concludes that the India-UAE CEPA is a promising FTA for India and provides important lessons for future trade agreements to maximise the trade potential existing with other major trade partners.

ملخص

(IUCEPA) تدرس هذه الورقة أثار اتفاقية الشراكة الاقتصادية الشاملة بين الإمارات والهند على تركيبة العلاقات التجارية الثنائية بين الهند والإمارات العربية المتحدة ومداهما. ولفهم تكامل هيكل التجارة وإمكانات التعاون التجاري، اعتمدت هذه الورقة مؤشرات مثل الميزة ، والقدرة التنافسية الظاهرة (RTA) ، والميزة التجارية الظاهرة (RCA) النسبية الظاهرة ، إلى جانب تحليل التخصص التجاري. ولفهم الأثر التجاري لاتفاقية الشراكة على كلا (RC) البلدين، تم استخدام نموذج الجاذبية المعزز مع تقنيتي التقدير: تفكيك متجهات الأثر

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وكشفت النتائج أن (PPML) ومقاربة الاحتمالية القصوى الزائفة لبواسون (FEVD) الثابت الهند طالما تمتعت على مر السنين بميزة نسبية أكثر استقرارا مقارنة بالإمارات العربية المتحدة. وهناك تكامل تجاري بين البلدين. ووهذا يعني أن ثمة أثر إيجابي لاتفاقية الشراكة الاقتصادية الشاملة، إذ تشير التوقعات إلى أن حجم التجارة بين البلدين سيبلغ 113 مليار دولار أمريكي في غضون خمس سنوات من تاريخ توقيع الاتفاقية. وتخلص الدراسة إلى أن هذه الاتفاقية تجسد اتفاقية تجارة حرة واعدة بالنسبة للهند، ويمكنها استخلاص تجارب قيمة منها لاستخدامها في الاتفاقيات التجارية المستقبلية لتعزيز المزايا التجارية القائمة مع باقي الشركاء التجاريين الرئيسيين.

RESUME

Cet article examine l'impact de l'accord de partenariat économique global entre l'Inde et les Émirats arabes unis (IUCEPA) sur la composition et l'ampleur du commerce bilatéral entre l'Inde et les Émirats arabes unis. Pour comprendre la complémentarité de la structure des échanges et le potentiel de coopération commerciale, le document utilise des indicateurs tels que l'avantage comparatif révélé (ACR), l'avantage commercial révélé (ACR) et la compétitivité révélée (CR), ainsi qu'une analyse de la spécialisation commerciale. Pour comprendre l'impact commercial de l'accord IUCEPA sur les deux nations, un modèle de gravité augmenté avec la décomposition vectorielle à effet fixe (FEVD) et les techniques d'estimation du pseudo-maximum de vraisemblance de Poisson (PPML) ont été utilisés. Les résultats révèlent que l'Inde a bénéficié d'un avantage comparatif plus stable que les Émirats arabes unis au fil des ans. Il existe des échanges complémentaires entre les deux pays. L'impact global du CEPA est positif, le commerce devant augmenter pour atteindre 113 milliards de dollars américains dans les cinq ans suivant la signature de l'accord. L'étude conclut que le CEPA Inde-Émirats arabes unis est un accord de libre-échange prometteur pour l'Inde et qu'il permet de tirer des enseignements importants pour les futurs accords commerciaux afin de maximiser le potentiel commercial existant avec d'autres partenaires commerciaux majeurs.

Keywords: India-UAE CEPA, India-UAE Trade, Gravity Model, Poisson

Pseudo-Maximum Likelihood (PPML) Estimation

1. Introduction

A staunch multilateralist for a long time, India shifted towards regionalism and signed many Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) due to changes in the global trade situations and to exploit trade gains existing with potential trade partners. Most of the early trade agreements India signed helped to improve trade and investment with the partners, but the gains from trade disproportionately went in favour of India's trade partners. After careful considerations, the India-UAE Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA), which was signed in February 2022 and came into effect in May 2022, tried to address some of the previous concerns by offering comprehensive sectoral coverage, provisions for balanced outcomes, a structured mechanism to address Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs), etc. UAE is India's third largest trade partner, and the agreement is expected to improve bilateral trade by US\$ 100 billion within five years. Assessing the potential gains from the India-CEPA agreement is extremely useful for India regarding the economic, strategic, and long-term trade policy formulation for sustained economic development through expanded trade engagements. A systematic study on the impact of the agreement can provide initial gains from increased trade flows and sectoral changes that provide useful insights for designing more productive trade agreements for India in the coming years.

UAE is an important trade destination for India as it acts as a gateway to Middle Eastern countries and Central Asian countries and acts as a hub for transporting goods to these regions. Some of India's traditional export items, such as agricultural products, pharmaceutical products, textiles and clothing, gems and jewellery, are exported to Middle Eastern countries, particularly the UAE and are expected to improve further with the CEPA agreement. India is looking for an alternative supply chain network after the COVID-19 pandemic. It is currently focused on developing the Middle East-Central Europe regions through the Middle East economic corridor, and the UAE plays an important facilitator in this effort.

Despite the region's significance, there are limited studies assessing the economic impact of the CEPA, particularly on expected trade creation, trade specialisation patterns, and competitiveness of sectors and products. Studies on the topic primarily looked at historical trade intensities and potential benefits, leaving scope for a comprehensive analysis of sectoral

complementarities, export competitiveness over time, and the extent of bilateral trade creation.

The study used comprehensive methodological approaches such as the construction of trade indicators, trade specialisation through convergence equations and a gravity model for calculating trade potential. Robust estimation techniques such as Fixed Effect Vector Decomposition (FEVD) and Poisson Pseudo-Maximum Likelihood (PPML) were used in the paper to address methodological issues related to the gravity model. By addressing these gaps identified from the literature, the paper provides a deeper understanding of the economic impact of the India-UAE CEPA. It offers valuable insights for formulating effective trade policy and RTA strategies.

2. Literature Review

Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) have been studied over the years to understand their impact on bilateral trade. Studies by Vicard (2009) and Freund et al. (2009) suggest that RTAs increase bilateral trade, while Chen et al. (2004) counters this, stating that due to RTAs, developing countries lose their exports. Mandharachalam et al. (2022) estimated potential trade gains from India's RTA and showed that India's GDP could improve by 4.1 per cent and can add US\$109.096 billion in 2030. Studies related to India, such as those by Siddiqui (2019) and Ahmed (2010), highlight the negative impact of RTAs on trade, increasing India's deficit with Japan and ASEAN, respectively, while Krishna (2021) and Kaushal (2021) have negated the point, showing improved export efficiency for India.

Many studies have tried to explore India-UAE relations. Using indices like Trade Intensity and Revealed Comparative Advantage, Alam et al. (2017) suggest a significant trade potential in various sectors. Goyal and Vajid (2016, 2018) highlight India and UAE's commitment to strengthening economic and trade ties, while Krishnaswamy and Shaw (2014) warn that the trade figures might be inflated due to the round-tripping certain commodities. Ismail and Ahmed (2022, 2024) estimate a trade creation of 70% with CEPA and emphasise the untapped bilateral trade potential. Similarly, Kanojia et al. (2024), using comparative and econometric analyses, found that CEPA has improved the trade volumes and investment figures between India and UAE, while Górski and Bhukya

(2024) highlight that CEPA has the potential to open India's procurement market to international competition, enhancing efficiency.

This study builds on methodologies used by Balassa (1965) and Fertö et al. (2003), applying Revealed Comparative Advantage to assess export specialisation, and Dalum et al. (1998) to assess the specialisation pattern over the years. It also employs the Gravity model introduced by Tinbergen (1962). To address the heteroscedasticity and to handle time-invariant variables in panel data, the two augmented gravity models are structured using the Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood Model by Silva and Tenreiro (2006) and the Fixed Effect Vector Decomposition (FEVD) model by Plümper and Troeger (2007).

While many researchers have tried studying the CEPA, a critical research gap is found in understanding the present India-UAE relations, especially in the specialisation pattern and gravity model-driven analysis. This study tries to fill that gap and assess the complementarities.

3. India's Trade Relations with UAE

India and UAE have a historical relationship dating back centuries. The bilateral trade between the two countries has steadily grown, making India UAE's top trading partner in 2008-09 and the UAE becoming India's top trading partner in 2012-13. India's top 5 imports from the UAE in the year 2021 based on 2-digit HS classifications were Mineral Fuels (27), Natural, cultured pearls (71), Plastics (39), Salt, Sulphur (25), and Iron and Steel (72) and the other imports included Jewellery, Minerals, Chemicals, and Wooden Products. India's top 5 exports to the UAE were in Natural, cultured pearls (71), Mineral Fuels (27), Electrical machinery and equipment (85), Iron and Steel (72), and Ships, boats, and floating structures (89), and the other important items include Food items, Textiles, Engineering Products, and Chemicals (UNComtrade).

The Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA) between India and the UAE, which came into force in May 2022, had an ambitious target of taking the trade in goods to US\$ 100 billion and the trade in services to US\$ 15 billion in 5 years from agreement's signing, which had already reached around US\$ 85 billion even before completing one year of the agreement (UNComtrade). The CEPA agreement allows a significant tariff concession of duty-free access on 97% of tariff lines by

the UAE to India, covering 99% of India's exports to the UAE, while India provides duty-free access for 90% of tariff lines. The UAE and India have agreed to apply immediate tariff elimination to 80.3% of the product line and 64.6% of the product line, respectively. The remaining tariff is scheduled for phased elimination (India Ministry of Commerce and Industry, 2022). The agreement has kept a tight 40% Rules of Origin (RoO) for most products to prevent routing products from others. The agreement provides enhanced market access to Indian service providers in about 111 sub-sectors, which include professional services, R&D, telecommunication, and audio-visual services. India has included a chapter on Government Procurement for the first time, and provisions were made for paperless trading and electronic authentication. In addition, the agreement had provisions on Intellectual Property Rights, Investment Promotion, SME Cooperation, Dispute Settlement and Labor and Environment. The agreement also kept significant provisions such as a special focus on cooperation in strategic sectors like defence, space, and nuclear energy, a fast-track approval process for Indian pharmaceutical products already approved in developed countries, duty-free access for Indian jewellery exports to the UAE and significant tariff reductions on Indian textile exports to UAE. This reduction in trade barriers is expected to help both economies in economic growth and diversification, fostering more dynamic bilateral trade relations.

UAE is an important strategic partner to India as it provides energy security and renewable energy requirements to India. UAE is a gateway to the broader Middle East, Africa, and Europe with air and sea connectivity, benefiting trade and tourism and exporting manufactured goods and services to the region. The huge Indian diaspora in UAE (about 3.5 million) is a cementing force in this relationship. India presents a huge opportunity to the UAE in terms of its vast consumer market, investment opportunities in infrastructure, energy, and technology and provides food security through agricultural exports. The India-Middle East-Europe corridor will reduce shipping costs substantially, provide easy access to Europe via the Middle East, create a new supply chain and provide an alternative to China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI).

4. Data and Methodology

The data for the study was collected from multiple sources, including UN Comtrade (classified under the harmonised system), World Integrated

Trade Solution (WITS), Centre d'Études Prospectives et d'Informations Internationales (CEPII), and the United States International Trade Commission. The bilateral trade between India, UAE, and the world was collected from the UN Comtrade using the WITS from 2000 to 2022 to calculate trade indices at HS 2 digits and 6 digits. The gravity model data were collected from 2000 to 2019 for 50 countries from the Centre d'Études Prospectives et d'Informations Internationales and WITS of the World Bank. The bilateral trade flows between the top 30 trading nations were used to create a panel dataset (unbalanced) with 46063 entries for FEVD and 45944 entries for PPML.

4.1. Tools of Analysis

The Balassa's Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for India and UAE is used to measure the trade competitiveness using the following formula:

$$RCA_{ij} = \frac{\frac{X_{ij}}{X_{it}}}{\frac{X_{wj}}{X_{wt}}} \quad (1)$$

Where: X_{ij} = Exports of product j by country i ; X_{it} = Total exports by country i ; X_{wj} = world (/Country k , in case of bilateral) exports of product j ; X_{wt} = Total world (/Country k , in case of bilateral) exports. An RCA value greater than 1 indicates a country's comparative advantage in a product. The bilateral RCA is calculated to see which country has an advantage over the other in the given products. A value above four is considered strong, between 2-4 is considered medium, and between 1-2 is considered weak/low (Hinloopen, 2001).

4.2. Model Specifications

The study used Specialisation/Despecialisation analysis to explain how countries' export patterns and comparative advantages evolve over time. This helps identify whether countries are becoming more specialised in certain industries or sectors or diversifying their export base. As a first step towards specialisation and de-specialisation analysis for India and UAE, Revealed Symmetric Comparative Advantage (RSCA) was calculated using the following formula:

$$RSCA_{ij} = (RCA_{ij} - 1)/(RCA_{ij} + 1) \quad (2)$$

An autoregressive regression model is run to check for the stability of the patterns over time:

$$RSCA_{ij2} = \beta_0 - \beta_1 RSCA_{ij1} + \epsilon_i \quad (3)$$

Where β_1 close to 1 indicates stability, greater than 1 indicates specialisation, and less than 1 indicates de-specialisation. The β_1 value below 0 indicates that the specialisation pattern has reversed. The base year for the analysis was set to 2000, except for 2016, which was used to assess the COVID-19 effect. 2004, 2008, 2012, 2016, 2020, and 2022 were taken as the current years individually to know the change in export patterns for India and UAE. Further, sigma specialisation was analysed with the formula β_1/R .

The gravity model of international trade is used to analyse the effects of various independent variables on bilateral trade flows between India and UAE. The Fixed Effect Vector Decomposition (FEVD) model was used to correctly analyse the impact of time-invariant and rarely changing variables in the panel data of the gravity model. The paper first estimated the fixed effect model to extract the unit effects. Then, we regress the unit effects from the first model on the time-invariant and rarely changing variables using OLS. The last step is to estimate a Pooled OLS model on the baseline model, including all the explanatory time-variant, time-invariant, and rarely changing variables while accounting for the residuals from the OLS model.

The FEVD Model is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(BT_{ij}) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln(GDP_i) + \beta_2 \ln(GDP_j) + \beta_3 \ln(Dist_{ij}) + \\ & \beta_4 FTA + \beta_5 Contiguity + \beta_6 Comofflang + \beta_7 Comethnolang + \\ & \beta_8 Comreligion + \beta_9 Comcol + \epsilon_{ij} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The PPML model is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} BT_{ij} = & \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln(GDP_i) + \beta_2 \ln(GDP_j) + \beta_3 \ln(Dist_{ij}) + \\ & \beta_4 FTA + \beta_5 Contiguity + \beta_6 Comofflang + \beta_7 Comethnolang + \\ & \beta_8 Comreligion + \beta_9 Comcol + \epsilon_{ij}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where BT_{ij} = bilateral trade flow between country i and j ; $\ln(BT_{ij})$ = natural log of bilateral trade flow; $\ln(GDP_i)$ = natural log of the GDP of country i capturing its economic size; $\ln(GDP_j)$ = natural log of the GDP of country j capturing its economic size; $\ln(Dist_{ij})$ = Distance between country i and j ; FTA = Dummy variable representing the free trade agreement between country i and j ; $Contiguity$ = Dummy representing the shared border between country i and j ; $Comofflang$ = Dummy representing whether country i and j share a common official language; $Comethnolang$ = Dummy representing whether country i and j share a common ethnic language; $Comcol$ = Dummy representing whether country i and j share a common colonial history.

Similar regressions are run with bilateral exports and imports as the dependent variables. The Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood (PPML) method of gravity model was used to handle heteroskedasticity in trade flow without using a log to check for the impact of the RTA on India-UAE trade.

5. Empirical Results

The results of the RCA analysis, specialisation/despecialisation of trade patterns and the change in the trade flows between India and UAE based on the gravity model are provided below.

5.1. RCA Analysis

RCA was calculated for India and UAE from 2000 to 2022 to understand the comparative advantage and its emergence. Over this period, both countries have experienced gains and losses in comparative advantage in HS product categories. Table 1 shows the HS 2-digit commodities in which India and UAE have had a significant loss since the year 2000-2003. As shown in the table, India has completely lost its advantage in product codes 08 and 26. India has lost its strength significantly in other products mentioned in the table, but it still enjoys a comparative advantage in those commodities. On the other hand, the UAE experienced a significant loss in only one product, HS-11, which has completely lost its comparative advantage.

Table 1: Significant RCA loss for India and UAE since 2000

INDIA							
Prod Code	Product Name	2000-2003	2004-2007	2008-2011	2012-2015	2016-2019	2020-2022
08	Fruit and nuts, edible; peel of citrus fruit or melons	2.467	1.656	1.118	0.927	0.793	0.600
13	Lac; gums, resins and other vegetable saps and extracts	14.287	10.514	10.103	19.441	7.379	5.276
26	Ores, slag, and ash	3.599	5.571	2.751	0.503	0.570	0.665
42	Articles of leather; saddlery and harness; travel goods	5.832	3.834	2.457	2.030	1.827	1.495
50	Silk	16.862	12.766	6.937	2.915	2.283	3.617
62	Apparel and clothing accessories; not knitted or crocheted	4.488	3.396	2.682	2.479	2.432	1.950
63	Textiles, made up articles; sets; worn clothing and worn textile articles; rags	8.355	6.486	4.076	4.188	4.558	3.372
71	Natural, cultured pearls; precious, semi-precious stones;	8.827	7,382	5.803	3.811	3.977	2.484
UAE							
Prod Code	Product Name	2000-2003	2004-2007	2008-2011	2012-2015	2016-2019	2020-2022
11	Products of the milling industry; malt, starches, inulin, wheat gluten	1.457	0.738	0.291	0.166	0.282	0.284
Note: Products with minor losses for India are not reported in the table.							

Source: Authors' Calculations

Table 2 shows the HS 2-digit commodities in which India and UAE have gained comparative advantages since 2000-03. For India, except for product code 17, all the other products listed, product codes 69, 76, 78, and 79, have shown a rise from having no comparative advantage to

having a comparative advantage, especially in the 10 years from 2012-2022. India maintains a strong comparative advantage in Sugar and Sugar Confectionery (17). On the other hand, UAE has shown a comparative advantage gain in products coded 24, 71, 74, and 75, and it maintains a strong comparative advantage in Tobacco (24).

Table 2: Significant RCA gain for India and UAE since 2000

INDIA							
Prod Code	Product Name	2000-2003	2004-2007	2008-2011	2012-2015	2016-2019	2020-2022
17	Sugars and sugar confectionery	2.245	1.600	2.058	1.866	2.003	4.815
69	Ceramic products	0.517	0.409	0.454	0.705	1.460	1.812
76	Aluminium and articles thereof	0.680	0.574	0.587	0.782	1.365	1.947
78	Lead and articles thereof	0.114	0.461	1.033	1.367	2.457	3.057
79	Zinc and articles thereof	0.198	1.499	2.983	2.343	2.280	2.913
UAE							
Prod Code	Product Name	2000-2003	2004-2007	2008-2011	2012-2015	2016-2019	2020-2022
24	Tobacco and manufactured tobacco substitutes	0.063	0.136	0.240	0.793	3.991	6.664
71	Natural, cultured pearls; precious, semi-precious stones;	0.031	0.552	2.593	2.731	3.188	3.332
74	Copper and articles thereof	0.060	0.069	0.236	0.720	1.370	1.141
75	Nickel and articles thereof	0.002	0.002	0.007	0.027	0.266	2.543

Source: Authors' Calculations

Table 3 highlights the HS 2-digit commodities with a strong RCA (4+) and how it has changed over the past two decades. India has always had a comparative advantage in the products listed above; coded 10, 13, 17, 52, 53, and 57; and India still maintains its comparative advantage in the above commodities. UAE maintains a strong comparative advantage in only two commodities, coded 24 and 27. UAE has always had a comparative advantage in Mineral Fuels (27), which it still maintains.

Table 3: Current strong Comparative advantage for UAE

INDIA		RCA Values					
Prod Code	Product Name	2000-2003	2004-2007	2008-2011	2012-2015	2016-2019	2020-2022
10	Cereals	3.995	3.846	2.652	4.348	3.700	4.298
13	Lac; gums, resins and other vegetable saps and extracts	14.287	10.514	10.103	19.441	7.379	5.276
17	Sugars and sugar confectionery	2.245	1.600	2.058	1.866	2.003	4.815
52	Cotton	9.208	7.359	7.301	8.480	7.003	7.419
53	Vegetable textile fibres; paper yarn and woven fabrics of paper yarn	5.978	4.887	5.115	4.690	6.445	6.910
57	Carpets and other textile floor coverings	9.810	8.894	5.954	5.980	6.361	6.548
UAE		RCA Values					
HS Code	Product Name	2000-2003	2004-2007	2008-2011	2012-2015	2016-2019	2020-2022
24	Tobacco and manufactured tobacco substitutes	0.063	0.136	0.240	0.793	3.991	6.664
27	Mineral fuels, mineral oils and products of their distillation;	7.562	4.725	3.245	3.037	4.658	6.684

Source: Authors' Calculations

Table 4 shows us the Bilateral Revealed Comparative Advantage in HS 2-digit commodities that the UAE enjoys over India currently. Of all the products listed, UAE enjoys a significant comparative advantage (4+) in only products coded 01, 24, 27, 47, and 75. In Copper and articles (74), the UAE enjoys a comparative advantage over India, but in all the other products, the bilateral advantage that the UAE possesses is just over 1. In all the other products, except those listed in Table 4, India enjoys a bilateral revealed comparative advantage over the UAE.

Table 4: Current bilateral RCA for UAE over India, year group 2020-2022

HS Code	Product Name	RCA 2020-2022	HS Code	Product Name	RCA 2020-2022
01	Animals; live	6.269	47	Pulp of wood or other fibrous cellulosic material; recovered (waste and scrap) paper or paperboard	37.091
04	Dairy produce; birds' eggs; natural honey	1.235	49	Printed books, newspapers, pictures and other products of the printing industry; etc.	1.650
18	Cocoa and cocoa preparations	1.730	71	Natural, cultured pearls; precious, semi-precious stones; etc.	1.345
19	Preparations of cereals, flour, starch or milk; pastrycooks' products	1.060	74	Copper and articles thereof	2.408
24	Tobacco and manufactured tobacco substitutes	5.043	75	Nickel and articles thereof	13.992
27	Mineral fuels, mineral oils and products of their distillation; bituminous substances; mineral waxes	5.136	76	Aluminium and articles thereof	1.055
39	Plastics and articles thereof	1.057	80	Tin; articles thereof	1.763

Source: Authors' Calculations

Table 5 gives the complementary HS-2 products between India and UAE for 2016-2019 and 2020-2022. There are five products in which India had a strong comparative advantage, and UAE had none in the year group 2016-19, which became 6 in 2020-2022. There were 37 products in which both countries enjoyed complementarity in the 2016-19 group, which became 39 in the 2020-22 group. There are 5-6 products in which both countries have a comparative advantage, but the intensity of comparative advantage is different, showing a possibility of complementarity.

Table 5: Complementarity between India and UAE 2016-19 & 2020-22

Trade Complementarity		2016-2019	2020-2022
India 4+	UAE <1	13, 52, 53, 57, 63	10, 13, 17, 52, 53, 57
India 2-4	UAE <1	03, 09, 10, 14, 29, 32, 50, 54, 55, 61, 62, 78, 79, 89	03, 09, 29, 32, 50, 54, 55, 63, 78, 79, 89
India 1-2	UAE<1	02, 12, 23, 30, 36, 38, 41, 42, 58, 64, 67, 68, 69, 72, 73	02, 11, 14, 23, 30, 36, 38, 40, 41, 42, 46, 58, 61, 62, 67, 68, 69, 72, 73
India <1	UAE 4+	99	-
India <1	UAE 2-4	-	75
India <1	UAE 1-2	49, 74	49, 74
India 1+	UAE 1+	17‡, 24‡, 25, 27‡, 71, 76‡	24‡, 25, 27‡, 71, 76
‡ shows potential for complementarity			

Source: Authors' Calculations

5.2. Stability of Export Specialisation

Table 6 highlights whether India and UAE are continuing with the specialisation they had in the year 2000 in the HS 2-digit products. There is β -de-specialisation as the β values are less than 1. This is true for both India and the UAE. This suggests that the products in which India and UAE had low RSCA are now tending towards higher RSCA, and the products in which they had high RSCA are tending towards lower RSCA. That accounts for the regression effect, but the mobility effect should be checked as β values are less than 1.

Table 6: Stability of export specialisation pattern for India and UAE

INDIA					
Assessment Year	Base Year	α	β	R	$\beta/R(\sigma)$
2004	2000	-0.001	0.844***	0.902	0.935
2008	2000	-0.001	0.759***	0.851	0.892
2012	2000	-0.039	0.691 ***	0.824	0.839
2016	2000	-0.024	0.640***	0.801	0.799
2020	2000	-0.001	0.598***	0.725	0.824
2022	2000	-0.046	0.532***	0.681	0.782
2020	2016	0.024	0.959	0.930	1.031

UAE					
Assessment Year	Base Year	α	β	R	$\beta/R (\sigma)$
2004	2000	-0.177**	0.763***	0.694	1.099
2008	2000	-0.313***	0.569***	0.468	1.216
2012	2000	-0.240**	0.592***	0.476	1.243
2016	2000	-0.054	0.715**	0.490	1.459
2020	2000	-0.044	0.726**	0.522	1.391
2022	2000	-0.083	0.689***	0.507	1.360
2020	2016	-0.182***	0.733***	0.768	0.954
Note: Since $\beta < 1$, we must consider β/R , which shows convergence					
Significance levels: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$					

Source: Authors' Calculations

The σ value for India is less than 1, suggesting a relatively lower mobility effect wherein the relative positions of products in India's export specialisation have not changed much, whereas the same is not true for the UAE. The σ value is greater than 1, suggesting that the products' positions in export specialisation have changed considerably for UAE. Table 7 shows the descending order of RCA strength for the HS 2-digit commodities for both India and UAE. For India, out of the products listed in the year group 2000-03, 7 are repeated in the year 2020-22. This number is restricted to only 3 for UAE. This further supports our analysis of specialisation patterns.

Table 7: Ranking of products with the highest comparative advantages for India and UAE

INDIA			
2000-03		2020-22	
Hs Code	Product Name	HS Code	Product Name
50	Silk	52	Cotton
13	Lac; gums, resins and other vegetable saps and extracts	53	Vegetable textile fibres; paper yarn and woven fabrics of paper yarn
57	Carpets and other textile floor coverings	57	Carpets and other textile floor coverings
52	Cotton	13	Lac; gums, resins and other vegetable saps and extracts
71	Natural, cultured pearls; precious, semi-precious stones; precious metals, metals clad with precious metal, and articles thereof; imitation jewellery; coin	17	Sugars and sugar confectionery
63	Textiles, made up articles; sets; worn clothing and worn textile articles; rags	10	Cereals
09	Coffee, tea, mate and spices	09	Coffee, tea, mate and spices
53	Vegetable textile fibres; paper yarn and woven fabrics of paper yarn	50	Silk
42	Articles of leather; saddlery and harness; travel goods, handbags and similar containers; articles of animal gut (other than silk-worm gut)	63	Textiles, made up articles; sets; worn clothing and worn textile articles; rags
14	Vegetable plaiting materials; vegetable products not elsewhere specified or included	78	Lead and articles thereof

UAE			
2000-03		2020-22	
Hs Code	Product Name	HS Code	Product Name
27	Mineral fuels, mineral oils and products of their distillation; bituminous substances; mineral waxes	27	Mineral fuels, mineral oils and products of their distillation; bituminous substances; mineral waxes
99	Commodities not specified according to kind	24	Tobacco and manufactured tobacco substitutes
76	Aluminium and articles thereof	71	Natural, cultured pearls; precious, semi-precious stones; precious metals, metals clad with precious metal, and articles thereof; imitation jewellery; coin
11	Products of the milling industry; malt, starches, inulin, wheat gluten	75	Nickel and articles thereof
25	Salt; sulphur; earths, stone; plastering materials, lime and cement	76	Aluminium and articles thereof
69	Ceramic products	25	Salt; sulphur; earths, stone; plastering materials, lime and cement
17	Sugars and sugar confectionery	74	Copper and articles thereof
15	Animal or vegetable fats and oils and their cleavage products; prepared animal fats; animal or vegetable waxes	17	Sugars and sugar confectionery
62	Apparel and clothing accessories; not knitted or crocheted	49	Printed books, newspapers, pictures and other products of the printing industry; manuscripts, typescripts and plans
89	Ships, boats and floating structures	39	Plastics and articles thereof

Source: Authors' Calculations

5.3. Gravity Analysis

The results of the two efficient estimation methods, namely the Fixed Effect Vector Decomposition Model (FEVD) and the Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood Model (PPML) of the gravity model, are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: FEVD and PPML Gravity Models

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables					
	ln (Bilateral Trade)	Bilateral Trade	ln (Exports)	Exports	ln (Imports)	Imports
	FEVD	PPML	FEVD	PPML	FEVD	PPML
$\ln(GDP_i)$	0.662***	0.747***	0.674***	0.725***	0.693***	0.766***
$\ln(GDP_j)$	0.573***	0.732***	0.629***	0.748***	0.594***	0.717***
$\ln(Dist_{ij})$	-1.254***	-0.553***	-0.374***	-0.583***	-1.621***	-0.525***
FTA	0.094***	0.247***	0.099***	0.302***	0.056***	0.200***
Contiguity	-0.288***	0.551***	1.580***	0.554***	-1.068***	0.546***
Comofflang	0.017	-0.354***	0.267***	-0.389***	0.004	-0.326***
Comethnolang	0.547***	0.437***	0.537***	0.488***	0.622***	0.392***
Comreligion	-0.693***	-0.549***	0.181***	-0.488***	-0.721***	-0.609***
Comcol	0.466***	0.212***	-0.084***	0.184***	0.508***	0.239***
Intercept	0.228***	-10.00***	-9.864***	-10.43***	1.487***	-10.96***
Observations	46063	45944	46063	45944	46063	45944
R ²	0.960		0.934		0.932	
Deviance based pseudo R ²		0.823		0.780		0.787

Note: Significance levels: * p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Source: Authors' Calculation

Bilateral trade, bilateral exports, and bilateral imports are the independent variables for running FEVD and PPML models, which gives six gravity equation results. All the variables in both models are highly significant, except for the Dummy representing a common official language, which does not show significance under FEVD with the dependent variables as bilateral trade and bilateral imports. Regarding trade elasticities with the GDPs of both nations, the PPML model shows higher elasticity for all three equations than the FEVD model by around 0.005-0.012% (FEVD $se \approx 0.002$). About Distance, the PPML model maintains stability in its coefficient at around -0.55, with a slight variation for the models with Exports and Imports. On the other hand, the FEVD has a larger range ($se \approx 0.003, 0.004, \text{ and } 0.005$), respectively. Under both models, FTA positively impacts bilateral trade, exports, and imports. FTA positively and significantly increased bilateral trade by 9.8% [= $(e^{0.094} - 1) \times 100$] under FEVD and 28% under PPML. CEPA will increase the exports for a country by 10.4% under FEVD and 35.3% under PPML. FTA will increase the imports by 5.7% based on the FEVD model and 22.1% under the PPML model. The R^2 suggests that the independent variables explain 96%, 93%, and 93% of the variations in dependent variables, namely bilateral trade, exports, and imports. The goodness fit for the PPML is measured with deviance-based Pseudo R2, which suggests that 82%, 78%, and 79% of the variations are explained by the independent variables for their respective dependent variables.

Since the implementation of CEPA, the only variables that have changed are the countries' GDPs and the FTA dummy. India and UAE are among the nations with top trade, thus naturally having a representation in the regression model. The trade was approximately US\$ 72.9 billion in FY2021-22, which rose to US\$ 84.5 billion in FY2022-23.

Table 9: 'Change in trade' predictions based on FEVD model 2022-23

Variables	2022-23 Growth	FEVD Coefficients	FEVD Change in Percentage (US\$) (72.9 base)	FEVD Change in value (in US\$ billion)
$\ln(GDP_{ind})$	7.2%	0.662	4.77%	3.48
$\ln(GDP_{UAE})$	7.9%	0.573	4.53%	3.30
FTA	Yes	0.094	9.8%	7.14
Total			19.1%	13.92
Source: World Bank (growth rates)				

Source: Authors' Calculations

Table 9 shows the absolute change in trade based on the estimated model, which shows that trade has increased by US\$ 13.9 billion. Thus, the predicted trade becomes US\$ 86.8 billion, which is very close to the actual figures of US\$ 84.5 billion. Let us try to predict the flow further based on the 2 GDP variables. Table 10 shows that by the end of the year, the trade is expected to grow to US\$ 91 billion. If the growth rates remain unchanged, the bilateral trade is projected to reach US\$97.9 billion in FY2024-25, US\$105.3 billion in FY2025-26, and US\$113.3 in FY2026-27.

Table 20: Change in trade predictions based on FEVD model 2023-24

Variables	2023-24 Growth	FEVD Coefficients	FEVD Change in Percentage (US\$) (72.9 base)	FEVD Change in value (in US\$ billion)
$\ln(GDP_{ind})$	8.2%	0.662	5.4%	4.56
$\ln(GDP_{UAE})$	3.6%	0.573	2.2%	1.86
Total			7.6%	6.422
Source: pib.gov.in (Growth rate India) wam.ae (Growth rate UAE)				

Source: Authors' Calculations

6. Discussion

The paper examined how the sectoral trade pattern between India and UAE changed and how the CEPA will likely influence bilateral trade. A close examination showed that products HS-10, 13, 17, and 24 were placed on the exclusion list due to strong comparative advantage for either India or the UAE, which could lead to dumping, revenue loss, and harm to the local industries. RCA analysis showed a significant RCA loss for India, but India did not let the RCA for most of the products fall below 1. On the other hand, the UAE experienced a significant loss of only one product. Both countries exhibit trade complementarity in around 39 products, with five products showing strong potential for mutual benefit.

Specialisation trends suggest that both countries are experiencing sectoral convergence. India still maintains most of its top RCA products (HS-50, 13, 57, 52, 63, 09, and 53) in the top 10 list even after a couple of decades. In contrast, many of their top 10 RCA products have been replaced by

some other products for the UAE. Three products (HS-27, 25, and 17) still need to be added to the list. This might be due to the rapid development and change that the UAE has gone through in the past three decades. The gravity model analysis showed that by the end of the 5th year after signing the agreement, the trade will reach US\$ 113 billion, a robust trade expansion. However, India should keep a close eye on its trade deficit with the UAE, which depends on oil imports, as there is a high possibility that it might widen in the future. However, the enhanced trade will generate jobs, increased consumer welfare, and other economic benefits for both nations.

Recently, the concessional duty rates under CEPA on gold and silver have led to a significant surge in imports from the UAE. Analysts argue for the withdrawal of these duty cuts under CEPA; otherwise, this can create a greater trade deficit, increased domestic competition, and a loss of revenue to the Indian Government (GTRI).

UAE has a small number of products with a competitive edge over India. Trade complementarity allows both nations to create trade and economic advancements when tariffs are phased out. Unlike the previous RTAs of India, this agreement is promising as it is carefully crafted with an important trade partner. This finding aligns with Ismail and Ahmed (2022), who indicated that CEPA resulted in 70% trade creation and 30% trade divergence, ultimately leading to a positive consumer surplus (Ismail & Ahmed, 2022).

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, the India-UAE CEPA has shown significant trade potential between India and the UAE due to the level of complementarity. The trade is expanding at the expected rate, with projected bilateral trade reaching US\$ 113 within the next five years. Both nations have effectively leveraged their comparative advantages, demonstrating strong trade complementarity. Challenges like the tariff concessions on gold and silver remains, which could disrupt CEPA's effectiveness. However, they could be avoided by renegotiating the key terms. The success of this agreement will help India reevaluate its approach towards negotiating future agreements and revisit existing RTAs to maximise their potential.

8. Limitations and Future Research

For the gravity model, bilateral trade flows of the top 30 trading nations were used to create the panel dataset, covering most of the global trade, to analyse the trade effect. The study focused on 2-digit HS products for constructing trade indices and specialisation, leaving scope for further research on 8-digit HS products open. Granular level analysis might be needed to check for the impact of CEPA at the intra-industry level.

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